

**Birth of The Idea of Federalism: A Comparative Study of Federalism
in India And Germany**

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Abstract:

This paper, Birth of the Idea of Federalism: A Comparative Study of Federalism in India and Germany, examines the historical evolution, institutional frameworks, and fiscal dynamics of federalism in both countries. Through a comparative analysis of contextualist and functionalist methodologies, the study highlights how India’s federal structure has been shaped by its socio-cultural diversity and economic imperatives, often resulting in a strong centralising tendency. In contrast, Germany’s model reflects a more decentralised approach, influenced by post-war reconstruction and national unification efforts.

The paper explores key dimensions of federalism, including the distribution of legislative powers, the balance of authority between central and subnational governments, and evolving fiscal arrangements. Notable developments such as the shift from cooperative to competitive federalism in Germany and the introduction of the Goods and Services Tax (GST) in India, which has redefined fiscal relations between the Centre and the States—are critically analyzed. The study concludes by assessing how these structural shifts impact the foundational ideals of federalism and the challenges they pose in a contemporary context.

Introduction:

Indian constitution was drafted with a centralising tendency, in matters of fiscal devolution and for that purpose the finance commission was established as a neutral body to accommodate the diversity of the states, to divulge the revenues between the centre and the states on a “needs” basis.¹ The German Basic Law was drafted as a provisional document, to facilitate the unification of Germany. Its federal provisions were thus not only ‘inward-looking’ but also ‘outward-looking’, that is to say, that the basic law, which later came on to be adopted as the constitution of Germany, was framed not to ensure stability of the structure it was but to lay the groundwork of a unified Germany.

¹ Nirvikar Singh, and Govinda Rao, *The Political Economy of Federalism in India*, Oxford India Paperbacks (Delhi, 2006; online edn, Oxford Academic, 18 Oct. 2012), <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780195686937.001.0001> Accessed 21 July 2023.

Theoretically, the basic law seems to be very decentralised, however, due to the fiscal arrangements, land governments (State governments) have little autonomy to fulfil their constitutional responsibilities.² Where the powers of the Land government seem to be eroded at the land level, it can be seen to have considerably increased at the Federal level, sometimes even “excessive” through indirect representation.³ The reforms, however, have been unsuccessful, in the context of the politico-economic divide of the economically stronger and weaker states. This has been contextualized in the already alleged “political blockade” which is a major hindrance to the conversion of political Ideas into policies.⁴

In India, the devolution of finances was the primary responsibility of the finance commission, however, the planning commission, and recently the GST Council seem to have captured this function. The states thus are stripped of their right to decision-making with respect to taxes in their sphere of competence.⁵ Another important factor that has impacted the autonomy of states is the tied devolutions in the form of grants in aid and centrally sponsored schemes. These tied devolutions do possess an important socio-economic impact on the states.⁶

Based on this literature, I would address two questions in this essay,

- “What is the Impact of the deliberations in the Indian and German constitutions that went into conceptualising the Idea of Federalism?” and
- “How have the contemporary political economies affected the existing federal structures, of both countries?”

I have applied a *contextualist comparative* method, to appreciate the contextual differences, in the institutional structures, that were informed by different historical conceptions of federalism. Based on this, I have undertaken a *functionalist* method of comparison, of the subsequent developments in the fiscal devolution mechanisms.

² Arthur B. Gunlicks, Fifty Years of German Federalism: An Overview and Some Current Developments, in Peter H. Merkl (ed), *The Federal Republic of Germany at Fifty the End of a Century of Turmoil*. (Palgrave Macmillan, USA 1999) 186-202

³ Carolyn Moore, Wade Jacoby (eds.), *German Federalism in Transition: Reforms in a Consensual State*. (Routledge, New York 2010)

⁴ Ziblatt, Daniel F. *Recasting German Federalism? The Politics of Fiscal Decentralization in Post-Unification Germany*. (Politische Vierteljahresschrift, vol. 43, no. 4, 2002) 624–652. JSTOR, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/24199513> Accessed 23 July 2023.

⁵ Thomas Isaac, R. Mohan, Lekha Chakraborty, *Challenges to Indian Fiscal Federalism*, (New Delhi, LeftWord Books, 2019).

⁶ K.S. Hari, ‘Cooperative Federalism: Implications for Social Sector Expenditure in India’, in Naseer Ahmed Khan (ed). *Challenges and Issues in Indian Fiscal Federalism* (Springer, Singapore 2018).

I have chosen a comparative study of India and Germany because it is from the latter that the ‘unamendability’ of federalism was transposed to India, and both nations have considerably changed their fiscal power-sharing schemes. Moreover, a similar timeline of political and constitutional shocks provides a guide as to how the structures of federalism have changed.

This paper will trace, the idea of federalism from its inception in the Constitution to its contemporary regime, primarily focusing on the division of fiscal resources to sub-national entities, to understand their real capacities to exercise their powers and duties in constitutionally determined arenas.

For this, the essay will be divided into 5 parts, the first part will deal with the historical underpinnings that have shaped the idea of federalism in India and Germany. The second part will deal with the federal institutional structures. The third part will explain the horizontal and vertical division of legislative and fiscal powers and the fourth part will draw a timeline of change in fiscal federalism in both the countries. The fourth part is then subdivided into two heads, fiscal power sharing in Germany and India respectively. The fifth part contains the concluding remarks.

1. Ideals of Federalism:

India’s nationhood has evolved over centuries, with traces of administrative unity emerging only during the later Mughal era. However, the sense of “Indianness” crystallized during the anti-colonial struggle, shaping the nation’s politics, economy, and society.⁷ Administration in British India was highly centralized⁸. During the deliberation on The Government of India Act 1935, in which Indian leaders had also participated, the British wished to have decentralised federal provisions, with the intention of watering down the national movement, these demands were vehemently opposed by the Indian National Congress and the Muslim league alike.⁹

The constitution of 1950, which heavily relied on the 1935 act, opted not to include its federal provisions. Moreover, after the passing of the Indian Independence Act of 1947, there was a lack of participation of the princely states in the drafting of the constitution.¹⁰

⁷ Bipin Chandra, Mridula Mukherjee & Aditya Mukherjee. *India After Independence*. (Penguin Books, New Delhi 1999).

⁸ Nirvikar (n 1); It was only after the Govt of India Act 1919, the government being essentially unitary, delved some authority to Provincial governments.

⁹ Ibid; The Simon Commission report too provided for sharing of income tax between the centre and provinces should be an important part of the fiscal arrangements.

¹⁰ Arun K Thiruvengadam, ‘India’s Constitutional Founding: An Enduring but Mixed Legacy’, in Kevin YL Tan, Ridwanul Hoque (eds). *Constitutional Foundings in South Asia*. (Hart Publishing, UK 2021) 37.

Germany's historical trajectory too, has seen many unification attempts before finally being unified in 1990, notably under Bismarck's Reich and the subsequent Weimar Republic¹¹. The Federal Republic had inherited the legacy of the North German Confederation, to account for the negotiated form of federal arrangement.¹²

Post-independence, India¹³ and Germany¹⁴ had very different aspirations and aversions as regards the federal structure they were to adopt. India, after partition, was tilted towards a strong centre, with little motivation for a consent-based federal structure.¹⁵ Germany, on the other hand emerging from the aftermath of Nazi centralized control and Berlin's division, aspired to strengthen regional autonomy through its Basic Law, laying the groundwork for a more decentralized system, to the extent of enumerating it as an 'unamendable' provision of the constitution.¹⁶ This contrast reflected differing ideals – India navigating a balance between the need for a strong centre in the face of the economic challenges ahead and the need for a more decentralised approach to include heterogeneity within the nation, while Germany pursued a decentralised reunification, with a federal system of "checks and balances" as well as a centralized fiscal structure that would answer to the post-war effects on the economy.

2. Federal Structures:

After looking at the different inspirations that guided the constitution formations of the two countries, we seem to find some basic structural similarities in the federal institutions. Both constitutions prescribe bicameral legislatures, although, on a closer look, we find nuances that significantly represent their historical contextualities.¹⁷

¹¹ Arthur (n 2).

¹² Wolfgang Renzsch, German Federalism in Historical Perspective: Federalism as a Substitute for a National State, (Publius, Autumn, 1989, Vol. 19, No. 4,) 17-33; Land governments negotiated their political privileges to "monarchical principle" in exchange for renouncing the right to leave the federation

¹³ India gained independence from British rule on August 15, 1947. The Constitution of India was adopted on January 26, 1950, marking the country's transition to a republic.

¹⁴ Germany gained independence from Allied rule on May 5, 1955, when the "London Debt Agreement" was signed, restoring full sovereignty to West Germany. The Basic Law (Grundgesetz), was adopted on May 23 1949, marking the foundation of the Federal Republic of Germany.

¹⁵ Chandra (n 7).

¹⁶ Kim Lane Scheppele, *Aspirational and aversive constitutionalism: The case for studying cross-constitutional influence through negative models*, (Oxford University Press, Vol 1, No. 2 2003) 296-324

¹⁷ Vicky C. Jackson, *Narratives of Federalism: Of Continuities and Comparative Constitutional Experience*. (Duke Law Journal 51, no. 1 2001). 223, 272-273: The benefits of cross-national borrowing are higher for adjudicating issues of individual rights than for federalism. "This is because federalism provisions of constitutions are often peculiarly the product of political compromise in historically situated moments, generally designed as a practical rather than a principled accommodation of competing interests."

In India, the parliamentary form of government inherited from its colonial past consists of the Lok Sabha (the lower house) and Rajya Sabha (the upper house).¹⁸ The Upper house consists of representatives from the state governments. Similarly, the German parliament in the Federal Republic which is the descendent of the North German Confederation and the German Empire, possess a structure resembling the then imperial legislature. It is a bicameral legislature comprising of –Bundestag (the lower house) and Bundesrat (the upper house) which represents the Land governments.¹⁹

The upper houses in both the nations, represent the states in proportion to the population of the state. A law to be passed by the parliament would require the assent of both houses. Money bill, being an exception in India, the significance of which will be dealt with later in the essay. Similarly, both constitutions provide for a dualist form of federal administration, where the primary administration machinery is that of the state.²⁰

3. Horizontal and Vertical Federalism

In 1858, the provincial governments depended completely on annual central allocations, since the Centre had authority over all revenues receipts and expenditures. The period from 1870 to the first world war, there could be seen a gradual decentralization of fiscal matters, however unaccompanied by a national Identity.

The Basic Law makes the *Bundesrat*, the focal point of “participation” of Land governments in legislative and policy matters, without exceptions, no bill can become law unless assented to, by both houses of the legislature. Thus most of the participation of the Land Governments is through a ‘horizontal division of legislative power’, where Land governments exercise great authority over both, the expenditure and borrowing decisions.²¹

On the other hand, the “vertical division” of power was in fact “unitary” in nature²². It is in this sense that it is argued that the basic law “seems” to bestow more power on the Land governments than they actually have²³. A long list of concurrent powers with no conception of

¹⁸ Articles 80-86 of the Indian outline the composition, qualifications, duration, sessions, and other important aspects of both the Lok Sabha and the Rajya Sabha in the Indian Parliament.

¹⁹ Articles 38-43 and 50-54 of the Basic law outline the composition, powers, functions, and procedures of both the Bundesrat and the Bundestag in the German federal legislative process.

²⁰ Basic Law for the Federal Republic of Germany, Article 83; The constitution of India, Article 162.

²¹ Carolyn (n 3).

²² Carolyn Moore, Wade Jacoby & Arthur B. Gunlicks (2008) Introduction: German Federalism in Transition? in Carolyn Moore and Wade Jacoby (eds). *German Federalism in Transition: Reforms in a Consensual State*. (German Politics, Vol.17 Issue 4, 2008) 393-407.

²³ Arthur B. Gunlicks, *Issues in German Politics*, (New York, Manchester University Press, 2003)

‘dual authority’, heightened by the fact that the federal legislature has virtually legislated on all the concurrent subjects and the “framework laws” have led some scholars to argue about the legal and political significance of the Land legislatures.²⁴

During the treaty of the European Union, the land governments had participated actively, and it resulted in an increased horizontal division of power to the Land governments through the Bundesrat.²⁵

The Indian constitution on the other hand in the context of a ‘vertical division of legislative power’, provided for a seemingly exhaustive list enumerating the subject matter, on which the states and centre could make laws.²⁶ In contrast, the German basic law merely states the legislative power of the federal legislature, providing that any residuary power shall entail to the Land Government²⁷.

On the other hand, the horizontal division of federal power in India seems to be diluted in fiscal matters, The most glaring example is the case of the “money Bill”²⁸. The special procedure established for money bill, provide little to no scope of any effective action by the Upper House of the Parliament, which is the body of the representatives of the state governments. Thus, In India, Money Bills can only originate in the lower house of the parliament, and the upper house has little to no authority in the matter of money bills.²⁹ The historical reasons may be traced back to the lack of participation of the princely states in the drafting of the constitution, after passing of the Indian Independence act³⁰.

²⁴Arthur (n 2).

²⁵ Ibid; At the end of the discussion on the impact of the Treaty on the European Union, negotiated in June 1992, the following changes had been achieved at the behest of the Land governments, (i) principle of subsidiarity was included in the TEU, (ii) The committee of the regions was created, though with advisory functions (iii) provisions were made for subnational ministers to represent member states in the council of ministers when their autonomous rights were affected, and amendments were subsequently made in Article 23 and 24 of the Basic Law.

²⁶ Chandra (n 7); The constitution of India, Article 246, along with the seventh schedule which provides for three lists– The central list, the State list, and the concurrent list. Both state and centre can make laws on matters enumerated in the concurrent list, but any law shall to the extent of repugnancy be void.

²⁷ Basic Law for the Federal Republic of Germany, Article 30.

²⁸ The Constitution of India 1950, Article 109, 110.

²⁹ Constitution of India, Article 110 (add explanation)

³⁰ Thiruvengadam chapter. , Also see final report od The Union Powers Committee “....Now that partition is a settled fact we are unanimously of the view that it would be injurious to the interests of the country to provide for a weak central authority which could be incapable of ensuring peace, of co-ordinating vital matters of common concern and of speaking effectively for the whole country in the international sphere.”

prominence in German legal circles in the early 1960s.³³ which served as building blocks in creating the “joint policy network” between the Federal and the Land governments in the late 1970s.³⁴

By the late 1970s, a complex system of joint decision-making (*politerkerflechting*) was in place. This “Joint decision” has been subject to (and in turn led to the reform in 2006) immense criticism as this model of collaborative decision-making, lacked transparency, thereby creating difficulties in attributing responsibility to any single level.³⁵

a) German Unification and Fiscal Federalism

Post the German Unification in 1990, there was immense political pressure for serious federal reforms premised on the idea of “fiscal decentralisation”. The Narrative of “cooperative federalism” was being swayed away with what was known as “competitive federalism”. The political lobbying was carried on by South German states, which were economically stronger.³⁶

This political push was primarily motivated against “economic equalization”³⁷ which was viewed as a “financial punishment” by the economically stronger states. In response to the developing pressure for fiscal reforms, in 2001 an agreement was reached at the Minister President Conferences, with the federal government agreeing to contribute much more to the regional redistribution scheme. This agreement although meant a lesser burden on the wealthier states, in fact, increased the dependence of the states on the federal government.³⁸

³¹ Arthur, (n 2); A major example of this joint decision-making mechanism is the 1969 finance reform, introduced in the form of Article 91A and 91B, supplementing the federal grants system under Article 104A.

³² Zibblatt, Daniel F. *Recasting German Federalism? The Politics of Fiscal Decentralization in Post-Unification Germany*. (Politische Vierteljahresschrift, vol. 43, no. 4, 2002) 624–652. JSTOR, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/24199513> Accessed 23 July 2023.

³³ Popularised by the Tröger Expert Commission. This commission was established by the joint Bund-Land Commission with the specific purpose of reforming financial relations between the German states (Länder) and the federal government during the 1960s.

³⁴ Carolyn (n 22).

³⁵ Entanglements between federal and Land politicians and civil servants in the Bundesrat, numerous commissions and committees between the federal and Land (including local) levels and among Land officials, mixed financing and political-administrative responsibility for higher education and various forms of economic development, and the complex system of fiscal federalism

³⁶ Zibblatt, (n 32).

³⁷ “*Länderfinanzausgleich*” (State Financial Equalization) system involves the redistribution of financial resources collected through taxes among the states. States with higher tax revenues contribute more, while those with lower revenues receive financial support.

It was only in 2006 that a grand political coalition led to significant reforms. The area of concurrent jurisdiction was reduced, and legislation on many of the subjects now contained an added requirement of “essential” that was to be satisfied.³⁹ Lander was also given the flexibility to deviate from the concurrent legislation on a few subjects. The concept of “framework legislation” was abolished, and some of its items were transferred to federal or concurrent lists.⁴⁰

Thus, the contemporary federal struggle in Germany may be viewed as emerging not between the federal government and the state but between the economically stronger lander and weaker landers.

ii. India:

In India, the division of fiscal powers of taxation between the centre and the states was vertical in nature, whereby income tax, corporate tax and excise (other than on alcoholic liquor for human consumption, petroleum and petroleum products) were exclusive under the control of the centre, whereas taxation on intra purchase or sale of goods with the states. Service tax was only introduced in 1994 by the centre, using the residuary powers. This tax base was later increased to form a large chunk of revenue generation.⁴¹

Since the tax base of the states was meagre and had to be supplemented by fiscal devolution from the centre. Before the 1990s the devolution of fiscal powers was low and was directed through the constitutional body— finance commission.⁴² The tax system that prevailed created a lethargy in revenue generation, due to the issues of multiple-point taxation and cascading effect. During this period the tax system was seen as an “officer-centred tax” with a lot of corruption and inefficiency.⁴³

³⁸ In the wake of the continuous calls for fiscal reforms in 2003, a federalism reform commission (*Kommission von Bundestag und Bundesrat zur Modernisierung der bundesstaatlichen Ordnung – KOMBO*) was formed. The commission, however, did not seem to achieve any significant changes, and succumbed to the much-alleged “political blockage”, one of the major issues that asked for reform

³⁹ Basic Law, Article 74 (2) The Federation shall have the right to legislate on matters falling within clauses 4, 7, 11, 13, 15, 19a, 20, 22, 25 and 26 of paragraph (1) of Article 74, **if and to the extent that the establishment of equivalent living conditions throughout the federal territory or the maintenance of legal or economic unity renders federal regulation necessary in the national interest.**

⁴⁰ Carolyn (n 22).

⁴¹ Thomas Isaac, R. Mohan, Lekha Chakraborty, *Challenges to Indian Fiscal Federalism*, (New Delhi, LeftWord Books, 2019); Also see Chandra (n 7).

⁴² Nirvikar (n 1).; See also The Constitution of India Article 280: The Finance commission.

⁴³ Thomas (n 41).

In 1978, amidst this, the Supreme Court, while deciding on the constitutional power of amendment of the parliament, and the justification of parliamentary supremacy in India, delivered the *Keshavananda* Judgement.⁴⁴ The Judgement introduced the concept of ‘basic features’, which are immune to being amended by the parliament.⁴⁵

The Idea of ‘basic structure’ was transplanted by the Indian Supreme Court in the context of answering a similar question, that had arisen in both nations: ‘To what extent the constitutional mechanism may be employed to change the constitution itself’ Federalism was made part of the basic structure of the constitution.⁴⁶ It was at this juncture that “federalism” was said to be one of the components of the basic structure of the Constitution.

It thus meant that the federal structure that existed in this period would become unamenable to any constitutional amendment.

a) Economic liberalization and states’ power to determine tax

After the drastic economic reforms that were brought about by the philosophy of liberalisation, privatisation and globalisation in 1990, for a few years the states enjoyed some spending freedom, to promote investments. This however led to the states offering tax holidays to corporate investors, which could only be called a “fiscal race to the bottom”.⁴⁷ This prompted the central government to introduce the VAT (Value added tax) on April 2005, with standard tax rates.

This standardization of rates though had been done consensually by the empowered committee of state finance ministers, attracted criticism, that the states were persuaded to surrender their constitutional right to fix tax rates. Another factor that significantly constrained the fiscal autonomy of the states in this period was the emphasis on “grants-in-aid and centrally sponsored schemes by the Central government, which not only forced the states to spend on their non-priority areas but also were meant to bear most of the financial burden of the scheme.”⁴⁸

⁴⁴ Kesavananda Bharati v. State of Kerala, (1973) 4 SCC 225.

⁴⁵ It is not to say that the text containing the basic features, would not be amenable to amendment, but that the spirit of the ‘basic structure’ would be the yardstick to assess the validity of any constitutional amendment.

⁴⁶ Mark Tushnet, ‘Some reflections on method in comparative constitutional law’ in Sujit Choudhry (ed.), *The Migration of Constitutional Ideas* (Cambridge University Press: 2006)67-83; On Normative universalism, Tushnet says “(these methods) Involve efforts to see how constitutional ideas developed in one system might be related to those in another, either because the ideas attempt to capture the same normative value or because they attempt to organize a government to carry out the same tasks.”

⁴⁷ Thomas (n 41).

⁴⁸ Ibid.

a) GST Council: the birth of competitive federalism

However, after 2015, the scenario changed, with a reduction in the centrally sponsored schemes to give way to higher untied tax devolution. Although this meant giving some spending autonomy to the states, it led to a significant decline in the allocation of funds towards social sectors.⁴⁹

Parallely the political homogeneity in the centre and the states led to the 101st constitutional amendment by which the Goods and Services Tax (GST) was introduced On July 1, 2017.⁵⁰ GST was the final blow to states' power to determine their taxes, which was already weakened by the VAT regime. After the 101st constitutional amendment, the states also seem to have lost the bargaining power in the GST council.⁵¹ Moreover, the spending autonomy is greatly curtailed since the apportionment of the total tax collection is 50:50, whereas the state taxes subsumed were 44% and central taxes subsumed were 25%.

When the constitution was made, the system of fiscal distribution was mapped on a "need basis", and such need would have to be determined by an independent constitutional body- the Finance Commission. In the contemporary fiscal structure under the GST regime, tax devolution is based on the revenue generated by the state and not its needs.

5. Concluding remarks:

It has to be kept in mind that India is a socio-culturally diverse nation, and had to have federalism in its basic structure of the constitution not only as a means of checks and balances but more importantly as a means of participation in a diversity of the socio-cultural needs of the states. In sharp contrast to Germany, with a much more homogeneous population, which adopted the Idea of federalism to restrict the possibility of majoritarian decision-making, which is reflected in the scarce devolution of power vertically, but increased interdependence of states and centre horizontally.

⁴⁹ K.S. Hari (n 6); This is a problem since Indian states historically have spent very little of their funds towards "social sectors"- especially on education and health, one of the major reasons for the backlog of human development across Indian States.

⁵⁰ Thomas (n 41); Accepting the impact, of the political scenario during the procedure of negotiations of the empowered committee of the state finance ministers, it cannot be ignored, that the inclusion of "services" in the state tax base, was a lure for states to accept the GST regime.

⁵¹ The reason is, the centre holds 1/3rd of voting rights, and all states together possess 2/3rd rights, but for any resolution to be passed in the Council, a 3/4th majority is required, conferring a practical veto to the central government.

While contemporary Germany is trying to cure, the vehemently criticised system of “joint decision making” causing a political blockade, it may be said that the GST regime in India is based on the same lines. Perhaps, it may be argued that in India the Centre’s encroachment in the vertical fiscal powers of the states, without the cushioning provided for in the horizontal sphere, like in Germany, would call for attention to the ‘basic structure’ of the constitution and the context in which it was transposed in India.

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Nirvikar highlights the need for an institutional assessment of federalism, which would consist of the elements of assignment of rights not only between the public and private sphere but also among the different levels of the government. An efficient allocation of such rights would require efficient "institution and structure of incentives"¹ These institutions and incentives in turn depend of political and economic factors, which would be influences by the allocation of rights, the incentives and the institutions.

¹ Nirvikar Singh, Oxford